

Evaluating the Effects of Financial Ratios, Company Size and Growth Opportunities on Value Added Toward Food and Beverage Industry Listed in IDX

Dahlia Dahlia^{1*}, Nurmauludiana M², Prasetya G Syarief³
Binaniaga Indonesia university

Corresponding Author: Dahlia Dahlia dahlialetter@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

The research to analyze value added company using financial ratios, company size and growth opportunities. High company value can have a positive impact on the company. This research period starts from 2017 to 2021, where in this period a pandemic occurs due to the spread of the Covid-19 which causes a decline in the world economy. 140 registered companies with method used was purposive sampling using The SPSS data processing. Profitability, liquidity, Company Size and growth simultaneously influence company value. The coefficient of determination is 84.5% while 15.5% comes from other variables.

INTRODUCTION

Company value measurement uses PBV (Price Book Value) ratio. If the company's share price is higher, the higher the company value, and added for company owners, because a high company value shows that the shareholders' abilities have good performance for investor. According to Bitu et al. (2021) The goal of business companies to have high price for value added because it will increase the prosperity of shareholders. Company value can be measured through several aspects, which reflects investors' overall assessment of each equity owned. Value added for stock market prices show the central assessment of all stock market players, acting as a perform company management. According to Dewantari et al. (2019), value added to high share prices will make the market believe in the future company's performance. The goals of company to increasing company profits and maximizing value added and will become important criteria for maintaining the company's survival.

The phenomenon that occurred in food & beverage industry listed IDX) in 2017-2021, where in period a pandemic occurs Covid-19 which causes a decline in the world economy are listed in the table below:

Table 1. Price Book Value (PBV) with Financial Ratios Food & Beverage Company Manufacture

NO.	The Average Ratio	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	Annual Average
1	Return On Asset	11,83	11,09	12,95	8,12	10,08	10,81
2	Current Ratio	2,58	2,68	2,79	2,75	2,50	2,66
3	Company Size	29,07	29,15	29,20	29,36	29,40	29,24
4	Growth Opportunities	0,17	0,09	0,05	0,23	0,05	0,12
5	Price Book Value	4,86	4,95	4,80	3,48	3,23	4,26

Source: Processed Data (2023)

From table 1, Price Book Value in 2017-2021 illustrates fluctuation, while in 2019 - 2021 the average Price to Book Value has decreases of stock market prices in the market while the annual average has increases. Return on asset in 2017-2019 has increases, but in 2019-2021 has fluctuations. The current ratio does not experience high fluctuations. but in contrast to growth opportunities, it has decreased since 2018 and increased in 2020 but decreased again in 2021. Company size has constant data with annual average, not affected with conditions, because the niche sample was selected based on being registered, have earning profits. Based on table 1, a comparison was made with the presentation of PBV data based on the sample used for each company:

Table 2. Price Book value (PBV) Food & Beverage Company Manufacture

NO	CODE	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
1	BUDI	0,35	0,35	0,36	0,34	0,58
2	DLTA	3,21	3,43	4,35	3,45	2,96
3	ICBP	5,11	5,37	4,89	2,22	1,85
4	INDF	1,43	1,31	1,28	0,76	0,64
5	MYOR	6,14	6,81	4,63	5,38	3,94
6	MLBI	27,06	28,87	28,50	14,11	14,66
7	ROTI	2,80	2,55	2,60	2,61	2,95
8	SKBM	1,21	1,15	0,68	0,58	0,63
9	SKLT	2,22	2,75	2,63	2,39	2,78
10	STTP	4,12	2,98	2,74	4,66	3,00
11	ULTJ	3,36	2,78	3,52	3,87	3,50
12	CEKA	1,36	1,04	1,35	1,35	1,29
ANNUAL AVERAGE		4,86	4,95	4,80	3,48	3,23

Source: Processed Data (2023)

Based on the sample data on table 2, PBV Food & Beverage manufacturing company illustrate fluctuation, to many factor that can affected PBV, can be traced using financial ratio analysis. The phenomena that occur in Indonesia regarding the development of the food and beverage industry.

Table 3. Gross Domestic Product at Constant Price Food & Beverage Company Manufacture

NO	YEAR	TRILLIUN (Rp)
1	2016	585.79
2	2017	639.83
3	2018	690.46
4	2019	744.17
5	2020	755.91
6	2021	775.1

Source: BPS, 2021

Based on data quoted from ukmindonesia.id, food and beverage industry from 2016 to 2021 recorded positive growth. Gross Domestic Product (GDP) at constant prices in 2016 was 585.79 trillion, in 2017 it was 639.83 trillion or an increase of 9.23% from the previous year. In 2018 it was 690.46 trillion, 2019 it was 744.17 trillion, 2020 it was 755.91 trillion and 2021 it was 775.1 trillion, where in 2021 it increased by 2.54%.

Financial ratios are considered to be the first factor that influences company value, a comparison between two related things, usually in the form of numbers, ratios, generally used to measure the ranking or financial position

of a company, from the financial side alone it can be seen that a company has good value. According to Yanti and Darmayanti (2019), food & beverage industrial sector is more stable and not easily affected by seasons or changes in economic conditions in terms of inflation remain guaranteed because this sector operates in Indonesia's basic industrial sector as company is non-cyclical in nature. The research problem will be concentrated on four factors. The first factor that affect company value is Profitability. According to Dewi and Sudhiarta (2017), Investors who invest shares in a company certainly have the aim of getting a return, where the higher the company's ability to generate profits, the greater the return investors expect, resulting in the company's value increasing.

The second factor is Liquidity. According to Permana and Rahyuda (2019), Liquidity used to measure a company's ability to pay the obligations that must be completed, will have a big impact on the value of the company in front of investors in making decisions because a high level of liquidity shows that the company is able to pay all its obligations owned both short and long term. Investors will judge that a company that has high liquidity is able to manage cash turnover. The third factor is company Size. According to Dewi and Sudhiarta (2017), Company size is a description of the company that shows the success of the company which can be reflected in the total assets owned by the company. According to Bitu et al. (2021), Company size describes the size of a company which can be seen from the level of sales and the number of assets owned by a company.

The fourth factor is growth opportunities. According to Suwardika and Mustanda (2017), company growth shows the company's ability to maintain its economic position. According to Saputri and Giovanni, (2021), company growth can be measured using Total Asset Growth (TAG).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Profitability

Profitability is generally calculated by looking for the excess difference between income and expenses. According to Husnan and Pudjiastuti (2015:76) profitability ratios are these ratios intended to measure how far a company's ability to generate profits from its sales, assets, or from the equity. According to Nur (2019) profitability is the ability of a company to make a profit in a certain period, a company that is able to generate large and stable profits will attract investors. In this research, profitability measurement will use the Return on Asset ratio scale (ROA). According to Fribontius and Hartoko (2022), Bitu et.al (2021), Satria (2021), Ambarwati and Vitaningrum (2021), Nuradawiyah and Susilawati (2020), Permana and Rahyuda (2019), Yanti and Darmayanti (2019), Ruslim and Michael (2019), Kusumawati and Setiawan (2019), Chasanah (2018), Rahmansyah and Jumahir (2018), Sucuachi and Cambarihan (2016), in their researches found the result that profitability has a positive effect on company value, but not consistent with research conducted by Wijaya et al., (2021) found the result profitability has a negative effect on company value.

H1: Profitability has a positive effect on PBV

Liquidity

The liquidity ratio proxied by the Current Ratio (CR). According to Saputri and Giovanni (2018) found the result that liquidity has a positive effect on company value but not consistent with research conducted by Yanti and Darmayanti (2019).

H2: Liquidity has a positive effect on company value

Company Size

Company size can be interpreted as a comparison of how large or small a business on a scale where certain classifications. According to D Dahlia, (2021) the company size is measured in various ways, including: total assets at the end of the year, share market value, number of employees, number of sales, market capitalization. According to Chasanah (2019), company size is the size of the company which can be seen from the size of the capital used, the total assets owned, or the total sales obtained. In this research, company size measurement is formulated with logarithm assets. According to Nuradawiyah and Susilawati (2020), found the result that liquidity has a positive effect on company value but not consistent with research conducted by Yanti and Darmayanti (2019).

H3: Company Size has a positive effect on company value

Growth Opportunities

According to Sormin and Genesisus (2021), growth opportunities are opportunities for company development in the future. The research conducted by Saputri and Giovanni (2021), found the result Growth Opportunities has a positive effect on company value but not consistent with research conducted by Ruslim and Michael (2019).

H4: Growth Opportunities has a positive effect on company value

CONTEXTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

This research was conducted to evaluate the effect of profitability, liquidity, size, Growth, on value added. The variables in this study consisted of four independent variables and one dependent variable. The independent variable in this study is profitability, liquidity, firm Size, and Growth Opportunities and the dependent variable in this study is firm value.

METHODOLOGY

The method research is quantitative, uses numerical and statistical analysis. The type of data used in this research is secondary data form financial reports published by companies in the 2017-2021.

Research Variable

The dependent variable in this research is value added (Y). The independent variables in this research are profitability (X1), liquidity (X2), company size (X3) and growth opportunities (X4). The operational variables are shown in Table 4 below:

Table 4. Operational Variables

Variables		Proxied	Scala
Y	PBV	Price Book Value = $\frac{\text{Market Price per Share}}{\text{Book Value per Share}}$	Ratio
X1	Profitability	Return On Asset = $\frac{\text{Net Income After Tax}}{\text{Total Asset}}$	Ratio
X2	Liquidity	Current Ratio = $\frac{\text{Current Asset}}{\text{Current Liability}}$	Ratio
X3	Size	Current Ratio = $\frac{\text{Current Asset}}{\text{Current Liability}}$	Ratio
X4	Growth	Growth Opportunity = $\frac{\text{Total Asset}_{(t)} - \text{Total Asset}_{(t-1)}}{\text{Total Asset}_{(t-1)}}$	Ratio

Source: Basics of Financial Management, Husnan and Pudjiastuti (2015)

Population and Sample

The criteria used by this research in taking samples are Food and beverage industry listed IDX 2017 to 2021,

Table 5. Stages Sample Selection

Descriptions	Companies	
		Data
Food and beverage industry listed	28	140
Food and beverage industry not listed	(10)	(50)
Food and beverage industry not present financial reports in Rupiah.	(0)	(0)
Food and beverage industry not consistently earn net profits.	(6)	(30)
Research Data	12	60

Source: Processed Data (2023)

Data analysis method

Data Quality Test (Residual Normality Test): The normality test in regression mode is used to test whether the independent variables and dependent variables in the regression model have a normal distribution or not (Purnomo, 2017:158). Data normality testing was used using one sample Kolmogorov Smirnov.

Classic Assumption Test: The classic assumption tests used in this research are the multicollinearity, heteroscedasticity and autocorrelation test.

Multiple Linear Regression: This analysis method aims to determine whether there is a relationship between the free variable and the bound variable, The linear equation for this research model is as follows:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \varepsilon$$

Y : Company Value
 α : Constant
 β₁ β₂ β₃ β₄ : Regression Coefficient
 X₁ : Profitability
 X₂ : Liquidity
 X₃ : Company Size
 X₄ : Growth Opportunities
 ε : Error

Hypothesis Testing

Correlation Coefficient Test: According to Santoso (2015) the analysis of correlation If $R < 0.5$ variable is weak, If $R \geq 0.5$ then the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable is strong.

Coefficient of Determination Test: The test is able to explain variations in the dependent variable and how much other variables that are not in the model explain variations in the dependent variable). The coefficient of determination test results shown by Adjusted R Square with the criteria (Ghozali, 2016).

If the Adjusted R Square value is close to 1, then the ability of the independent variable to predict variations in the dependent variable is stronger;

If the Adjusted R Square value is close to 0, then the ability of the independent variable to predict variations in the dependent variable is getting weaker.

t test: According to Ghozali (2016), the t test is used to find out whether there is an individual influence between the independent variable (X) on the dependent variable (Y). This test can be seen with the following criteria:

If $t \text{ count} < t \text{ table}$, then the null hypothesis (H_0) is accepted and the alternative hypothesis (H_a) is rejected;

If $t \text{ count} > t \text{ table}$, then the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected and the alternative hypothesis (H_a) is accepted;

Determining significance based on the following criteria:

If the sig value. $\geq (0.05)$, then the independent variables individually have no effect on the dependent variable;

If the sig value. $< (0.05)$, then the independent variable individually has an effect on the dependent variable.

F test: This test is carried out by comparing the critical value F (F table) with the calculated F value contained in the analysis of variance table from the calculation results:

If $F \text{ count} < F \text{ table}$, then the null hypothesis (H_0) is accepted and the alternative hypothesis (H_a) is rejected;

If $F \text{ count} > F \text{ table}$, then the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected and the alternative hypothesis (H_a) is accepted.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Data Quality Test

Table 6. Residual Normality Test

N		60
Normal Parameters	Mean	0.0000000
	Std. Deviation	2.32430811
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	0.111
	Positive	0.111
	Negative	-0.082
Test Statistic		0.111
As. Sig. (2-tailed)		0.062 ^c

Source: Output Data SPSS IBM 26

From table 6, the residual data normality test can show that the asymp. sig (2-tailed) is 0.062, so it can be concluded that the residual data is normally distributed, because the asymp. sig (2-tailed) is $0.062 > 0.05$.

Multicollinearity Test

Table 7. Multicollinearity Test

Model	Coefficients				Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t		Tolerance	VIF
	B	Std. Error	Beta				
1 (Constant)	7.807	6.680		1.169	0.248		
RETURN ON ASET	55.717	3.187	0.911	17.482	0.000	0.966	1.035
CURRENT RATIO	-1.214	0.174	-0.371	-6.973	0.000	0.925	1.081
COMPANY SIZE	-0.214	0.225	-0.053	-0.949	0.347	0.851	1.175
GROWTH	-0.704	1.293	-0.030	-0.545	0.588	0.889	1.125

Source: Output Data SPSS IBM 26

The table test show that all variables value less than 10, shows that there is no multicollinearity, which means there is no relationship between the independent variables, so data on profitability ratios, liquidity ratios, company size and growth opportunities are good for use in the regression model.

Heteroscedasticity Test

The results of the heteroscedasticity test in this study are presented in the following table:

Table 8. Heteroscedasticity Test

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.081	4.076		0.265	0.792
RETURN ON ASET	5.839	1.945	0.380	3.003	0.004
CURRENT RATIO	-0.065	0.106	-0.080	-0.615	0.541
COMPANY SIZE	0.009	0.138	0.009	0.063	0.950
GROWTH OPPORTUNITIES	-0.545	0.789	-0.091	-0.690	0.493

Source: Output Data SPSS IBM 26

The table shows that the significance value of the liquidity ratio (CR) variable is 0.540, company size (SIZE) is 0.950 and Growth Opportunities (GO) is 0.493 > 0.05, so it can be concluded that all these variables do not contain heteroscedasticity, meaning that there is no inequality of variance. from the residual of one observation to another observation in the regression model. Meanwhile, for the profitability variable (ROA), the significance value is 0.004 < 0.05, this shows that in the profitability ratio (ROA) variable there is heteroscedasticity.

Autocorrelation Test

The results of the autocorrelation test in this study are presented in the following table

Table 9. Autocorrelation Test

Model	R	R Square ^b	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	0.393 ^a	0.154	0.076	2.26001986	1.876

Source: Output Data SPSS IBM 26

Autocorrelation test obtained a DW value of 1.876., it can be seen in the Durbin Watson table where the number of samples (n) is 60 and the number of variables (k) is 4, so the DU value is 1.7274 and dL is 1.4443. So from the results of the analysis that has been carried out, the DW value of 1.876 is greater than the upper limit (du) of 1.7274 and less than 4-du (4-1.7274 = 2.2726) or can be denoted as 1.7274 < 1.876 < (4-1.7274) or du < d < 4 - du, it can be concluded that there is no autocorrelation.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

The results of the multiple linear regression analysis test in this study are presented in the following table:

Table 10. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	7.877	6.681		1.179	0.243
	RETURN ON ASET	0.557	0.032	0.910	17.475	0.000
	CURRENT RATIO	-1.214	0.174	-0.371	-6.969	0.000
	COMPANY SIZE	-0.216	0.225	-0.053	-0.959	0.342
	GROWTH OPPORTUNITIES	-0.684	1.293	-0.029	-0.529	0.599

Source: Output Data SPSS IBM 26

The results of multiple linear regression analysis obtained the regression equation:

$$Y = 7,877 + 0,557X1 - 1,214 X2 - 0,216X3 - 0,684 X4 + \varepsilon$$

Interpretation of Results

The constant value from the results of the equation above is 7.877, which means that if value of profitability (ROA), liquidity (CR), company size and growth opportunities increases by one unit, then the company value will increase by 7.877, assuming it remains constant or 0.

The *profitability* variable (X1) based on the results of regression calculations shows a positive coefficient value of 0.557 with a positive sign, which means that with a 1% increase in ROA, the value of the company value increases by 0.557 with the assumption that profitability (ROA) is considered fixed or constant. The *liquidity* variable (X2) based on the results of regression calculations shows a negative coefficient value of -1.214. This shows that with a 1% increase in liquidity (CR), the value of the company value decreases by 1.214 with the assumption that CR and company value are considered fixed or constant. The *company size* variable (X3) based on the results of regression calculations shows a negative coefficient value of -0.216. This shows that with a 1% increase in company size, the value of the company decreases by -0.216, assuming that the company size and company value are considered fixed or constant. The *growth opportunity* variable (X4) based on the results of regression calculations shows a negative coefficient value of -0.684. This shows that with a 1% increase in growth opportunities, the value of the company value decreases by -0.684, assuming that the growth opportunities and company value are considered fixed or constant.

Hypothesis Test

Correlation coefficient test

The results of the correlation coefficient test in this study are depicted in the following table:

Table 11. Correlation Coefficient Test

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.925 ^a	0.856	0.845	2.408101

Source: Output Data SPSS IBM 26

The table shows that R is greater than 0.05, namely 0.925, meaning the relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables is strong.

Coefficient of Determination Test

The results of the coefficient of determination test in this study are depicted in the following table:

Table 12. Coefficient of Determination Test

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.925 ^a	0.856	0.845	2.408101

Source: Output Data SPSS IBM 26

The Adjusted R² value is 0.845, meaning that statistically the percentage of variation in the dependent variable of company value that can be explained by variations in the independent variables of profitability ratio, liquidity ratio, company size and growth opportunities is 84.5%. The remaining 15.5% is explained by variations in other variables that were not included in the regression model in this research.

T -test

The results of the t test in this study are depicted in the following table:

Table 13. T test

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	7.877	6.681		1.179	0.243
	RETURN ON ASET	0.557	0.032	0.910	17.475	0.000
	CURRENT RATIO	-1.214	0.174	-0.371	-6.969	0.000
	COMPANY SIZE	-0.216	0.225	-0.053	-0.959	0.342
	GROWTH OPPORTUNITIES	-0.684	1.293	-0.029	-0.529	0.599

Source: Output Data SPSS IBM 26

T table formula:

$$T_{table} = t(\alpha/2; n-k), t = (0,025; 60-5), t = (0,025; 55) = 2,004$$

Profitability (ROA)

From the t test shows that profitability (ROA) has a t count of 17.475 with a significance level of 0.000. which means ROA has an effect on company value.

Liquidity (CR)

From the t test shows that liquidity (CR) has a t count of -6.969 with a significance level of 0.000. This shows that the significance level is below 0.05, means that liquidity (CR) has a significant negative effect on company value.

Company Size (Size)

The t count of -0.959 with a significance level of 0.342. This shows that the significance level is above 0.05, means company size has no effect on company value.

Growth Opportunity (GO)

The t test calculations of -0.529 with a significance level of 0.599. This shows that the significance level is above 0.05. which means that growth opportunities (GO) have no effect on company value.

F - Test

The results of the F test in this study are depicted in the following table:

Table 14. F test

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1893.102	4	473.276	81.632	0.000 ^b
	Residual	318.872	55	5.798		
	Total	2211.974	59			

Source: Output Data SPSS IBM 26

F table with the following formula:

$$F_{table} = F(k-1; n-k) F = (5-1; 60-5) / F = (4; 55) = 2,540$$

(Based on F table which is attached to this research).

From the results of the analysis test above, it is known that F count is 81.631. The significance is $0.000 < 0.05$ and F count is greater than F table, namely $81.631 > 2.540$, then H5 is accepted, meaning that there is a simultaneous influence between profitability, liquidity, company size and growth opportunities on company value.

Effect of Profitability on PBV

H1 is accepted, namely that ROA effected on PBV

This is proven by the significance value of 0.000 being smaller than 0.050, and the t count value of 17.475 being greater than t table which is 2.004. This research also shows a positive direction, because the regression coefficient value is 0.557.

Effect of Liquidity on PBV

H2 is accepted, namely that CR effected on PBV.

This is proven by the significance value of 0.00, which is smaller than 0.050, and the t count value of -6.969 is smaller than t table, namely 2.004. This research also shows a negative direction, because the regression coefficient value is -1.214.

Effect of Company Size on PBV

H3 is rejected, namely that company size (size) no effected PBV.

This is proven by the significance value of 0.342 which is greater than 0.050, and the t count value of -0.959 which is smaller than t table which is 2.004.

Effect of Growth Opportunities on Company Value

H4 is rejected, namely that growth opportunities (GO) no effected on PBV.

This is proven by the significance value of 0.559 which is greater than 0.050, and the t count value of -0.529 which is smaller than t table which is 2.004.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Evaluating the effects of financial ratios, company size and growth opportunities on value added toward food & beverage industry listed in IDX)

The hypothesis test to evaluating the effect of financial ratio profitability, liquidity, company size and growth opportunities on PBV. The dependent variables in this research, profitability, liquidity, company size and growth opportunities together effected on PBV.

ADVANCED RESEARCH

Researchers realize that knowledge and experience both theoretically and practically are limited. In the future, hoped that this research will be able to present higher quality research results regarding several things including, tax ratio, capital structure, and other ratios, another research samples, not limited food and beverage industry, can add data to overcome data that is not normally distributed.

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